

Mutations that abolish Pikm-1:ancHMA autoactivity are inadequate for testing the impact of AVR-PikD binding on Pikm-mediated immunity

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ABSTRACT

This Technical Note complements our paper on the evolution of the integrated HMA domain of the Pik-1 immune receptor (Białas et al., 2021). Pikm-1:ancHMA is autoactive when co-expressed with Pikm-2 and therefore cannot be directly used to study how changes in binding to the AVR-PikD effector affect the activation of immune responses. Here, we identified mutations that abolish Pikm-1:ancHMA autoactivity. Unfortunately, these mutations either (i) perturbed the response to AVR-PikD or (ii) affected protein stability. This precluded reliable studies of how the strength of AVR-PikD binding to Pikm:ancHMA correlates with activation of cell death response.

BACKGROUND

Previous research revealed that Pikip-1 and Pikm-1, two NLR immune receptors of rice, evolved towards high-affinity binding to the rice blast effector AVR-PikD from a weaker ancestral form, ancHMA (Białas et al., 2021). Pikip-1 and Pikm-1 evolved to bind AVR-PikD with high affinity by acquiring independent mutations in two distinct regions within their HMA domains; Pikip-1 evolved to interact with AVR-PikD in the IAQVV/LVKIE region, whereas Pikm-1 acquired adaptive mutations in the MKANK/EMVKE region. While gain of AVR-PikD binding in Pikip-1 correlates with the ability to trigger an immune response, we didn't determine whether the same applies to Pikm-1. This Technical Note reports experiments that aimed at addressing whether mutations that abolish Pikm-1:ancHMA autoactivity can be used to experimentally test for a correlation between AVR-PikD binding and activation of cell death.

RESULTS

The autoactivity of the Pikm-1:ancHMA fusion is compromised in Pikm-1:ancHMA_{IVDPM} and Pikm-1:ancHMA_{FFE} mutants

We undertook an experiment to determine whether mutations that affect AVR-PikD binding—located within the MKANK/EMVKE region—translate to an immunoactive Pikm-1. To test that we assessed the ability of Pikm-1:ancHMA fusion and previously described chimeras, namely Pikm-1:ancHMA_{EMVKE}, Pikm-1:ancHMA_{FFE}, Pikm-1:ancHMA_{STSN}, Pikm-1:ancHMA_{VH}, and Pikm-1:ancHMA_{IVDPM} (Bialas et al., 2021), for the ability to activate cell death (**Figure 1A**). In contrast to Pikm-1 and Pikm-2, used as a negative control, transient co-expression of the Pikm-1:ancHMA fusion with Pikm-2 in *N. benthamiana* led to cell death (**Figure 1**). The autoactivity was compromised in two out of five chimeras, Pikm-1:ancHMA_{IVDPM} and Pikm-1:ancHMA_{FFE}, and was not due to reduced protein accumulation level as shown in Bialas et al. (2021).

Wild-type Pikm-1 triggers cell death in response to AVR-PikD when transiently co-expressed with Pikm-2 in *N. benthamiana* (De la Concepcion et al., 2018). To check if the Pikm-1:ancHMA chimeras are also responsive to this effector, we co-expressed each of the Pikm-1:ancHMA mutants with Pikm-2 and AVR-PikD. The results varied between the constructs; while autoactive chimeras and Pikm-1:ancHMA_{FFE} were not responsive to AVR-PikD, Pikm-1:ancHMA_{IVDPM} co-expression with the effector resulted in cell death (**Figure 1**). This result was surprising because in our complimentary Bialas et al. (2021) paper, we didn't observe detectable association between Pikm-1:ancHMA_{IVDPM} and AVR-PikD in co-immunoprecipitation (co-IP) experiments.

Combination of the FFE and EMVKE mutations in Pikm-1:ancHMA affected protein accumulation level

Next, we leveraged the FFE mutations to test if the Pikm-1:ancHMA mutants that affect AVR-PikD binding, namely in the MKANK/EMVKE region, can activate immune response upon AVR-PikD binding. We introduced FFE mutations into Pikm-1:ancHMA—henceforth called Pikm-1:ancHMA_{FFE}, Pikm-1:ancHMA_{FFE-EMANK}, and Pikm-1:ancHMA_{FFE-EMVKE}—and tested their ability to activate cell death in *N. benthamiana* in response to AVR-PikD (**Figure 2A**). The Pikm-1:ancHMA_{FFE} and Pikm-1:ancHMA_{FFE-EMANK} mutants triggered cell death when transiently co-expressed with Pikm-2 and AVR-PikD (**Figure 2B–D**). However, the strength of this response was weak and inconsistent between experiments (**Figure 1C**). Also, Pikm-1:ancHMA_{FFE-EMVKE} did not trigger cell death, probably due to low accumulation level as noted by western blot analysis (**Figure 2E**). These results prevented correlating the cell death response with the strength of the AVR-PikD–Pikm:ancHMA binding.

CONCLUSIONS

In this Technical Note, we showed that Pikm-1:ancHMA is autoactive when co-expressed with Pikm-2 (**Figure 1**). We further identified that the Pikm-1:ancHMA_{FFE} and Pikm-1:ancHMA_{IVDPM} mutations abolish this autoactivity. Unfortunately, we were unable to utilise these mutants to study how changes in binding to the AVR-PikD effector affect the activation of immune responses.

First, Pikm-1:ancHMA_{IVDPM} triggered cell death upon co-expression with AVR-PikD (**Figure 1B–D**), despite the fact that we didn't detect any association between these proteins in the co-IP assays (Bialas et al., 2021). One possible explanation is that the lack of association was due to low sensitivity of the in planta co-IP assays. Another possibility is that Pikm-2 alters the dynamics of the interactions between Pikm-1 and the effector. It is important to note that the co-IP experiments were performed in the absence of Pikm-2 and therefore it is possible that this helper NLR facilitates the AVR-PikD–Pikm-1 interaction, for instance by stabilising the protein complex.

Second, in contrast to Pikm-1:ancHMA_{IVDPM}, Pikm-1:ancHMA_{FFE} did not respond to AVR-PikD (**Figure 1B–D**). This marked difference between these chimeras suggests that mutations that abolish Pikm-1 autoactivity can simultaneously modulate effector binding and thus interfere with the aim of our experiments.

Third, the Pikm-1:ancHMA_{FFE} mutants yielded inconsistent results, with the Pikm-1:ancHMA_{FFE} and Pikm-1:ancHMA_{FFE-EMANK} occasionally exhibiting weak autoactivity (**Figure 1B–D; Figure 2B–D**).

Finally, combination of the FFE and EMVKE mutations in Pikm-1:ancHMA_{FFE-EMVKE} affected protein accumulation level (**Figure 2E**), resulting in inconclusive results.

Altogether, these results precluded answering the question of how AVR-PikD binding correlates with activation of cell death in Pikm-1:ancHMA. Although we were unable to experimentally address this question, we put forward a hypothesis that Pikm-1 evolution towards strong binding to the AVR-PikD effector was likely an important milestone to render immunoactive Pikm-1. The MKANK/EMVKE region is located within well-characterised effector-binding interfaces 1 and 3 of the integrated HMA domain (De la Concepcion et al., 2018). Interface 3 is a major determinant of AVR-Pik binding in Pikm-HMA, resulting in Pik-mediated immune response in *N. benthamiana* and fungal resistance in rice (De la Concepcion et al., 2018; 2019; 2021; Kanzaki et al., 2012). De la Concepcion et al. (2018) have also shown a correlation between the strength of effector–Pikm-HMA interaction and cell death response. This suggests that evolution towards high-affinity binding to AVR-PikD was important for Pikm-mediated immunity. However, to what extent other evolutionary events, such as coevolution with Pikm-2, contributed to the receptor pair evolution remains to be determined.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The N-terminally Myc-tagged AVR-PikD, C-terminally HA-tagged Pikm-2, and C-terminally HF-tagged Pikm-1, Pikm-1:ancHMA, Pikm-1:ancHMA_{EMVKE}, Pikm-1:ancHMA_{FFE}, Pikm-1:ancHMA_{STSN}, Pikm-1:ancHMA_{VH}, and Pikm-1:ancHMA_{IVDPM} constructs were previously cloned by Bialas et al., (2021) and De la Concepcion et al., (2018). The ancHMA_{EMANK} mutant was generated by amplification and fusion of the N-terminus of ancHMA_{EMVKE} construct and the C-terminus of ancHMA. The ancHMA_{FFE-EMVKE} and ancHMA_{FFE-EMANK} mutants were synthesised by GENEWIZ (South Plainfield, NJ, USA) as Golden Gate modules. The ancHMA mutants corresponded to 187–264 residues of the full-length Pikm-1 protein and were subsequently assembled with custom-made p41308-PikmC (ISL SynBio) level 0 acceptor to generate Pikm-

1:ancHMA fusion. Obtained modules were then used to generate Pikm-1:ancHMA expression constructs, featuring C-terminal HF tag, in Golden Gate assembly with pICSL13004 (Mas promoter, TSL SynBio), pICSL50001 (C-terminal HF, TSL SynBio), and pICH77901 (Mas terminator, Addgene no. 50341), by Golden Gate method into pICH47732 binary vector (Addgene no. 48000).

Transient expression in *Nicotiana benthamiana* leaves was conducted as previously described (Bos et al., 2006). Cell death, was scored 5 days after agroinfiltration, using a previously published scale (Segretin et al., 2014) modified to range from 0 (no visible necrosis) to 7 (confluent necrosis).

The Western blot protocol used in this study was described previously (Bialas et al., 2021; Win et al., 2011).

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

We thank Phil Robinson of JIC Bioimaging facilities for photography. This work was supported by the Gatsby Charitable Foundation, Biotechnology and Biological Sciences Research Council (BBSRC, UK), the European Research Council (ERC, grant: proposal 743165) (SK, MJB), and BBSRC Doctoral Training Partnership at Norwich Research Park (grant: BB/M011216/1, project reference: 1771322) (AB). In addition, MJB receives funding from BBSRC (BB/P012574, BB/M02198X) and the John Innes Foundation.

COMPETING INTERESTS

SK receives funding from industry on NLR biology.

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Figure 1. Substitutions within the FFE and IVDPM regions compromise autoactivity of Pikm-1:ancHMA fusions. **(A)** Schematic representation of wild-type Pikm-1 and Pikm-1:ancHMA fusions used in the assay. The mutated regions are presented with arrowheads and listed. **(B)** Representative images of cell death assay after transient co-expression of the Pikm-1:ancHMA mutants (C-terminally tagged with HF) with AVR-PikD (N-terminally tagged with Myc) and Pikm-

2 (C-terminally tagged with HA). Empty vector (ev) was used as a negative control. Co-expression of Pikm-1, Pikm-2 and AVR-PikD was used as a positive control. All constructs were co-expressed with the gene silencing suppressor p19 (Win and Kamoun, 2003). **(C)** Cell death response was scored at five days post-infiltration. The results are presented as a dot plot where a size of a dot is proportional to the number of samples (count) with the same score within the same biological replicate. The experiment was independently repeated at least three times with 21–24 internal replicates; the columns within tested conditions (labelled on the bottom) correspond to results from different biological replicates. **(D)** Statistical analysis of HR cell death presented in panel C conducted using an estimation method using besthr R library (MacLean, 2019). Each panel corresponds to a different HF-tagged Pikm-1:ancHMA mutant (labelled above) co-expressed with Myc:AVR-PikD (D) or empty vector (ev); all constructs were co-expressed with Pikm-2. The left panels represent the ranked data (dots) and their corresponding mean (dashed line). The size of a dot centre is proportional to the number of observations with that specific value. The panels on the right show the distribution of 1000 bootstrap sample rank means, with the blue areas illustrating the 0.025 and 0.975 percentiles of the distribution. The difference is considered significant if the ranked mean for the co-expression with AVR-PikD falls beyond the blue percentile of the mean distribution for co-expression with the empty vector.

Figure 2. *Pikm-1:ancHMA_{FFE-EMVKE}* shows low level of in planta accumulation which prevents correlation of the strength of HR and AVR-PikD binding affinity. **(A)** Schematic representation of wild-type *Pikm-1* and *Pikm-1:ancHMA* fusions used in the assay. The mutated regions are presented with arrowheads and listed. **(B)** Representative images of HR cell death assay after transient co-expression of the *Pikm-1:ancHMA_{FFE}* mutants (C-terminally tagged with HF) with AVR-PikD (N-terminally tagged with Myc) and *Pikm-2* (C-terminally tagged with HA). Empty vector (ev) was used as a negative control. Co-expression of *Pikm-1*, *Pikm-2* and AVR-PikD was used as a positive control. All constructs were co-expressed with the gene silencing suppressor p19 (Win and Kamoun, 2003). **(C)** Cell death was scored at five days post-infiltration. The results are presented as a dot plot where a size of a dot is proportional to the number of samples (count) with the same score within the same biological replicate. The experiment was independently repeated at least three times with 10–24 internal replicates; the columns within tested conditions (labelled on

the bottom) correspond to results from different biological replicates. **(D)** Statistical analysis of HR cell death presented in panel C conducted using an estimation method using `besthr` R library (MacLean, 2019). Each panel corresponds to a different HF-tagged *Pikm-1:ancHMA* mutant (labelled above) co-expressed with *Myc:AVR-PikD* (D) or empty vector (ev); all constructs were co-expressed with *Pikm-2*. The left panels represent the ranked data (dots) and their corresponding mean (dashed line). The size of a dot centre is proportional to the number of observations with that specific value. The panels on the right show the distribution of 1000 bootstrap sample rank means, with the blue areas illustrating the 0.025 and 0.975 percentiles of the distribution. The difference is considered significant if the ranked mean for the co-expression with *AVR-PikD* falls beyond the blue percentile of the mean distribution for co-expression with the empty vector. **(E)** Western blot showing in planta accumulation of the *Pikm-1:ancHMA_{FFE}* mutants used in panels B and C. *Pikm-2* (C-terminally tagged with HA) was included as a negative control. Proteins were immunoblotted with the FLAG antisera. Rubisco loading control was performed using Pierce™ staining solution. The black arrowheads indicate expected band size. The figure shows results from three independent experiments.